

MAGNETO-MECHANICAL ACTUATION OF FERROMAGNETIC SHAPE MEMORY ALLOY COMPOSITES

Susanne Glock, Luis P. Canal, Véronique Michaud

Laboratoire de Technologie des Composites et Polymères (LTC),
Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), CH 1015 Lausanne, Switzerland
Email: veronique.michaud@epfl.ch, web page: <http://ltc.epfl.ch>

Keywords: Smart Materials, Functional Composites, Shape Memory Alloy, Magnetic actuation, Finite elements

ABSTRACT

Shape memory alloys are smart materials that are able to dissipate energy when strained and change their shape in a controlled manner when subjected to an external stimulation. The slow kinetics of heat transfer, however, limits the actuation potential of thermally activated shape memory alloys to low frequencies. Ferromagnetic shape memory alloys (MSMA) can be activated at constant temperature by a magnetic field, making MSMA promising candidates for applications requiring damping and isothermal, high frequency actuation. Ni-Mn-Ga alloys exhibit a magnetic field induced strain (MFIS) caused by twinning of theoretically up to 10 %. Polycrystalline Ni-Mn-Ga, however, is brittle and grain boundaries hinder twinning and suppress MFIS. Embedding slender single crystalline MSMA elements into a polymer matrix can thus provide composites with adjustable magnetic strain actuation behaviour that are at the same time easily handled and shaped.

In the present work, we investigated the actuation behaviour of composites made with Ni-Mn-Ga single crystalline rods embedded into epoxy. The rods were first characterized independently for their magneto-mechanical behaviour, which was described with a model quantifying the strain of the MSMA as a function of the magnetic field and applied stress. Composites were produced by embedding rods in soft epoxy matrices (2.5 and 9 MPa moduli) with different volumetric fractions, 13 and 34 vol.pct. Magnetic actuation of the composites was measured and shown to depend on the Ni-Mn-Ga volumetric fraction and the matrix stiffness. This behaviour was compared to finite element simulations of the composite actuation including the MSMA material model and an elastic model for the matrix. Agreement was satisfactory for prediction of the long-term behaviour using the relaxed modulus of the matrix. However, time-dependent actuation was found to result from the viscoelastic behaviour of the epoxy matrix at room temperature. Guidelines for composite actuation prediction could thus be proposed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermal shape memory alloys, such as NiTi based materials, present actuating properties that are of interest for practical applications requiring large strains and recovery stresses but they are restricted to low frequencies (about 1 Hz), as a consequence of the relatively slow process of thermally induced martensite to austenite phase transformation [1,2,3]. Nonetheless, under the form of thin wires, they have been embedded into host matrices or composite materials to provide shape change, actuation or a shift in vibration frequency [2,3]. Ferromagnetic shape memory alloys (MSMA) are a new class of shape memory alloys that show deformations up to 10% and 20% in their martensitic state, upon the application of an external magnetic field or mechanical load, respectively [4]. This response is caused by the reorientation of twins in the tetragonal or pseudo-tetragonal martensite phase. Since twinning is a very fast process, high actuation frequencies of up to 2 kHz can be reached, and new applications can be envisaged [5-7]. Grain boundaries, however, increase the twinning stress, hinder twinning and prevent the magnetic field induced actuation. Thus, applications requiring high strain and actuation frequency have been up to now limited to expensive and brittle single crystals.

An elegant alternative is to produce composites that contain single crystalline powders or slender fibres of Ni-Mn-Ga with grains as large as the fibre diameter. These composites are in principle more easily shaped for a given application, easier to handle, and suitable for applications with tailored magnetic actuation behaviour. So far, mostly powder composites have been produced [5,8,9] and have demonstrated very little Magnetic Field Induced Strain (MFIS), of less than 0.1% [10,11]. The use of MSMA fibres in composites is still in its infancy. Composites have been produced with melt-spun fibres in epoxy matrices and evaluated for damping [12-14]. Gans et al. investigated the use of single crystal rods in a PU resin and showed promising actuation strain results with one volume fraction of NiMnGa in the composite, in two simple geometric configurations, which they compared to an analytical isostrain model [15]. They also pointed out the beneficial role of the matrix material as a bias force to allow cyclic actuation behaviour. Linear actuators with high strain output and high frequency, albeit with moderate force output, could then be conceived with this configuration. However, no model was yet proposed and validated to optimize design of such actuators taking into account the influence of matrix stiffness and MSMA volume fraction on the one-dimensional magnetic actuation of continuous unidirectional MSMA elements embedded in a polymer matrix.

In the present work, we investigated the actuation behaviour of composites made with Ni-Mn-Ga single crystalline rods embedded into epoxy. The rods were first characterized independently for their magneto-mechanical behaviour, which was described with a model quantifying the strain of the MSMA as a function of the magnetic field and applied stress. Composites were produced by embedding rods in soft epoxy matrices. Magnetic actuation of the composites was measured and compared to finite element simulations of the composite actuation including the MSMA material model and an elastic model for the matrix. The role of matrix viscoelasticity was also pointed out.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ni-Mn-Ga rods were purchased from Adaptamat, Finland, and had a 10M structure. They were delivered with a stabilizing surface treatment and a dimension of $20 \times 1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$. To guarantee elongation along the long sample axis, the crystals had their faces parallel to the $\{100\}$ faces of the high temperature austenitic phase. In addition, the crystals were trained to activate only one out of the three possible twinning planes $\{101\}$, $\{011\}$ and $\{110\}$. Thus, the single crystals could only transform between two different twin variants, variant 1 and variant 2 and the twinning strain upon magnetic and mechanical activation took place only in the directions x , which is the long axis of the rod and y [16]. All rods were cut with a wire saw to obtain 10 mm long samples.

Figure 1: Schematic of the produced samples with low and high V_f , left, and picture of the corresponding produced samples, right.

Two epoxy systems of low modulus were selected: LME 10435 (resin)/LME 10436 (hardener) from Huntsman with a mix ratio of 100:123 by weight and SR 8150 (resin)/SD 815 B1 (hardener) from Sicomin with a mix ratio of 100:16 by weight. Four model composite specimens each containing four Ni-Mn-Ga single crystalline rods embedded in the epoxy matrix were manufactured to investigate the magnetic actuation behaviour of MSMA composites, with two different Ni-Mn-Ga volume fractions (13 and 34 vol.%), as shown in Figure 1. Samples were cast and cured at room temperature for 21 days, to avoid crossing the martensitic transformation temperature of the alloy (about 50°C).

The magneto-mechanical actuation of the rods and of the composites was measured using an in-

house set-up, consisting of dipole electromagnet 5403 from GMW associates, a micrometre screw and a force sensor (isolated with a glass rod from the sample) to simultaneously measure force and displacement under magnetic field. The full description of the set-up is given in ref. [17]. This set-up was used to determine the stress-strain compression behaviour of the rods after magnetization at 1.2T perpendicular to the long sample axis, their magnetic field induced stress (MFIS) for different pre-loads, as well as the actuation behaviour of the composites. For this last test, the strain versus time curves were recorded as the epoxy resins were viscoelastic at room temperature.

DSC was performed on the resin samples cured at room temperature, and at the recommended higher temperature cure cycle to determine the T_g of the resins, using a DSC Q100 from TA Instruments, with heating and cooling rates of 5°C/min. Stress-strain behaviour of the resins was measured by tensile tests carried out on dog-bone specimens with a gage length of 25 mm. The samples were cast in a silicon mould and cured at room temperature for the same time as for the Ni-Mn-Ga composites. Quasi-static tests of the tensile epoxy samples were performed on an electromechanical testing machine from Walter+Bai Ag, Switzerland, equipped with a 50 N load cell and extensometers. A first series of tests was performed at 50mm/ min, and a second series with lower speeds that were defined based on the time to reach the maximal value of strain in the actuation tests. As a result, the crosshead speeds selected for the tests with the two epoxy systems were 0.11 mm/min and 0.0026 mm/min for the LME 10435/LME 10436 and the SR 8150/SD 815 B1, respectively.

A magneto-mechanical material model was proposed to predict the strain upon twinning in a magnetic field, or through mechanical stress. Full description of this model is given in ref. [17]. The mechanical behaviour was shown to follow a first linear mode, then a pseudo-plastic deformation through twinning that could be modelled by a Tresca yield criterion, then followed by an elastic deformation at the end of the plateau-twinning region. The internal variable was the volume fraction of variants 1 and 2. The magnetic field induced behaviour was modelled using equivalent stress acting in the longitudinal direction, which magnitude depends on the magnetic field, through a sigmoid function.

The material model was then introduced in the commercial Finite Element Code Abaqus as a user materials model (UMAT). Both material phases were considered, at this stage an elastic model was used for the matrix material. The elastic modulus of the matrix was taken as the secant modulus of the quasistatic stress-strain curves of the epoxy, up to a strain corresponding to the maximum MFIS of the rods. A modulus of 2.5MPa for the LME 10435/LME10436, and of 9MPa for the SR8150/SD815 B1 were thus experimentally found and introduced in the model.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Ni-Mn-Ga rods

Figure 2(a) illustrates a typical compressive stress-strain curve, and Figure 2(b) a stress-magnetic field curve of a single crystalline Ni-Mn-Ga rod. The stress plateau of 2.4 MPa at high magnetic fields corresponds to the macroscopic maximum force effect of the magnetic field.

Figure 2: (a) Stress strain behavior of the single crystal, (b) stress-magnetic field behaviour.

The maximum stress induced by an external magnetic field is slightly higher than the twinning stress, indicating that the twins in the specimen can be activated by applying a magnetic field over 1 T [18]. Thus, a full reorientation of the martensitic variants is expected by the application of a magnetic field.

Figure 3 shows the experimentally obtained MFIS of a Ni-Mn-Ga single crystal for five different pre-loads. No noticeable MFIS was observed for low magnetic fields (below 0.22 T) since the stress induced by the field was not sufficient to induce twin boundary motion. With increasing magnetic field, more and more twinning takes place transforming the microstructure from the short sample state (variant 1) to the long sample state (variant 2) and resulting in an increasing MFIS. For high magnetic fields, the MFIS asymptotically reached a plateau indicating that no further twin boundary motion was possible. With increasing pre-load along the long sample axis and perpendicular to the field, the MFIS rise was shifted to higher magnetic fields and the maximum MFIS decreased from 5.3 % at no pre-load to 0.2 % at 2.4 MPa. Thus, for no pre-load, the MFIS approximately corresponds to the final twinning strain obtained in the compression test. However, the MFIS is almost blocked for a pre-load corresponding to the maximum force effect of the magnetic field.

Figure 3: Magnetic field induced strain of a single crystalline Ni-Mn-Ga rod for different pre-loads.

The constitutive behaviour of the rods was then established using the proposed model [16], as indicated on the solid lines in Figures 2 and 3. Stress and MFIS versus Magnetic Field show a very good agreement, a reasonable agreement is found for the stress strain curve, as our model assumes a sharp transition before and after the plateau region, which is in reality more progressive.

3.2 Epoxy resin

DSC results, reported in Figure 4 and Table 1, confirmed that the T_g of the soft resins is below room temperature and that curing is satisfactory, even at room temperature for 21 days. Tensile tests carried out at 5mm/min allowed characterizing the resins for their modulus, strength and failure strain, as reported in Table 1. In addition, quasi-static tensile stresses were performed to find the relaxed modulus of the resins, which was much smaller for the SR system, indicating a strong viscoelastic effect at room temperature for this epoxy.

Figure 4: DSC thermograms of the LME resin, left, and SR resin, right, on resins cures at two different curing conditions, recommended, or 21 days at Room Temperature.

Epoxy system	Curing conditions	T_g , cycle 1 (°C)	E-modulus (MPa)	Strength (MPa)	Strain at failure (%)	E modulus (MPa) quasistatic
LME 10435/ LME 10436	7 h at 80 °C	-22				
	21 days at RT	-24	2.4 ± 0.2	0.78 ± 0.04	41 ± 1	2.5
SR 8150/ SD 815 B1	24 h at 60 °C	18				
	21 days at RT	13	202 ± 10	14 ± 1	106 ± 4	9

Table 1: Properties of the epoxy resins.

3.3 Composites

Experimental results and numerical predictions of the magnetic field induced strain of all four Ni-Mn-Ga single crystal composites for an increasing magnetic field are shown in Figure 5. The constraining effect of the matrix is clearly demonstrated, the stiffer matrix leading to a lower MFIS for similar volume fractions. Effect of rods volume fraction is also demonstrated. Moreover, the results show that for 34% rods in the soft LME matrix, full actuation to 5% is already reached. However, these results also confirm the limitation of the MSMA materials that are easily restricted by the presence of a matrix, as the compressive forces that built up in the strained matrix are high enough to partly hinder twinning. Adapting the Ni-Mn-Ga volume fraction and/or the matrix stiffness can hence regulate the maximum actuation strain of Ni-Mn-Ga single crystal composites.

The simulations were able to reproduce the onset of twinning, the increase of the MFIS and the saturation of the MFIS in the high range of magnetic fields. The maximum strains obtained from the simulations are in good agreement with the experiments for the four composites specimens. The small deviations between the experiments and the simulations are attributed to the simplified stress-strain behaviour and to the use of the same stress-magnetic field curve for all Ni-Mn-Ga single crystals, whereas small variations were found between single crystals.

Figure 5: Numerical predicted magnetic field induced strains of the Ni-Mn-Ga single crystal epoxy matrix composites compared to the experimental results.

Figure 6 illustrates the influence of Ni-Mn-Ga volume fraction and matrix stiffness on the maximum MFIS, using the FE simulations with the model values for the fully characterised single crystal and the iso-strain model. The iso-strain model seems to underestimate the maximum MFIS of composites for all Ni-Mn-Ga volume fractions and matrix stiffness. This is expected since the analytical iso-strain model does not take into account the geometry of the composite, the shape and distribution of the Ni-Mn-Ga single crystals in the matrix and inhomogeneous strains in the composite. In particular, at low volume fraction MSMA, around 5 to 10 %, with a matrix modulus below 5 MPa, strains already above 2.5 % can be easily attained, and these are not well predicted with the analytical model. As a result, our simple model developed and implemented in a finite element code is able to realistically predict the actuation behaviour of Ni-Mn-Ga single crystal-polymer matrix composites. As input parameters, only the experimental stress-strain and stress-magnetic field curves of the Ni-Mn-Ga single crystals as well as the matrix stiffness are required to compute the composite strain upon actuation.

Figure 6: Comparison of the influence of Ni-Mn-Ga volume fraction and matrix stiffness on the maximum MFIS according to the FE simulations and the iso-strain model results.

Figure 7 illustrates the numerical predictions for the volumetric fraction of variant 2 evolved by twin boundary motion from variant 1 at a magnetic field of 1.3 T for all four Ni-Mn-Ga single crystal composites. Twinning is complete in the single crystals embedded with 34 vol.% Ni-Mn-Ga in the epoxy system LME 10435/LME 10436, and is only partially complete for the other three composites even for high magnetic fields. Thus, the forces developed in the matrix SR 8150/SD 815 B1 and LME 10435/LME 10436 (for a Ni-Mn-Ga volume fraction of 13 vol. %) are high enough to partly hinder twinning. Furthermore, the transformation of variant 2 is not homogeneous along the Ni-Mn-Ga single crystal. At the surface, less stress builds up in the matrix allowing the crystals to transform more extensively closer to the top free surface of the composite.

Figure 7: Simulated volumetric fraction of variant 2 evolved by twinning from variant 1 at a magnetic field of 1.3 T for the Ni-Mn-Ga single crystals embedded in epoxy. The samples drawn are the upper half of one single crystal out of the 4 in the composites.

3.3 Viscoelastic effect in the composite response

The previous model was developed assuming a constant elastic modulus of the matrix, and showed good agreement if we consider the relaxed secant modulus of the epoxy for the matrix modulus. Figure 8 reports MFIS measurements for the two Ni-Mn-Ga single crystal-epoxy matrix composites with a Ni-Mn-Ga volume fraction of 34 vol. % as a function of time after application of a constant magnetic field of 1.2 T. For both composites, the MFIS progressively increases with time under the applied load exerted by the rods. For the LME 10435/LME 10436 matrix composite, a quasi-static state was achieved much faster than for the SR 8150/SD815 B1 matrix composite. This can be related to the low modulus of the LME resin and weak sensitivity to strain, as shown in Table 1, which does not hinder the MFIS of the rods. For the SR resin, however, a marked viscoelastic behaviour was demonstrated in the tensile tests results in Table 1, and the stiffness at higher speed is rather high, 200 MPa, thus constraining the initial MFIS behaviour, and letting it take place over a longer time range.

The experimental MFIS-time curves is fitted using a standard linear solid model consisting of a spring in series with a spring and dashpot in parallel, by the exponential function representing creep under a constant load:

$$\varepsilon_{MFIS,comp}(t) = \frac{\sigma}{E_I} + \frac{\sigma}{E_{II}} \left[1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_0}} \right] = \varepsilon_{elastic} + \varepsilon_{viscous} \left[1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_0}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where σ is the stress, E_I and E_{II} and the moduli of the elastic springs I and II, t the time and τ_0 the relaxation time.

Figure 8: Time dependent magnetic field induced strains of the two Ni-Mn-Ga single crystal composites with a Ni-Mn-Ga volume fraction of 34 vol. %.

Since the applied stress in our case is not directly measured, and corresponds to the stress imposed on the resin by the MSMA under the magnetic field, we identify parameters $\epsilon_{\text{elastic}}$ and $\epsilon_{\text{viscous}}$, which correspond to the resulting elastic deformation, and viscous final deformation, respectively. All fit parameters as well as the calculated times to reach 95% strain for both flexible epoxy systems are summarised Table 2. The epoxy system SR 8150/SD815 B1 has a considerably longer relaxation time than the epoxy system LME 10435/LME 10436. Consequently, the instantaneous strain of the LME 10435/LME 10436 composite is with $\sigma/E_1 = 0.05$ (92 % of the maximum strain) considerably higher than that of the SR 8150/SD815 B1 composite with 0.009 (22 % of the maximum strain).

Thus, for actuation of Ni-Mn-Ga composites, beyond a simple stiffness consideration, the matrix behaviour should be tuned carefully to match the desired effect, either to reach a slow process and progressive actuation, or to ensure fast actuation.

Epoxy system	$\epsilon_{\text{elastic}}$	$\epsilon_{\text{viscous}}$	τ_0 (s)	Time to reach 95 % strain (min)
LME 10435/ LME 10436	0.05	0.004	1318	10
SR 8150/ SD815 B1	0.009	0.031	3063	141

Table 2: Model parameters and relaxation times of the epoxy system LME 10435/LME 10436 and SR 8150/SD815 B1 determined from time dependent MFIS measurements on the 34 vol. % Ni-Mn-Ga composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Ni-Mn-Ga single crystal-epoxy matrix composites were successfully produced and their magneto-mechanical behaviour was characterized. Depending on the Ni-Mn-Ga volume fraction and matrix stiffness, twinning was partially hindered by stresses developing in the matrix resulting in a reduction of the maximum magnetic field induced strain. Nonetheless, large actuation strains could be obtained with the low modulus matrix already with realistic volume fractions of MSMA rods. Finite Element simulations taking into account the magneto-mechanical behaviour of the MSMA rods and the elastic behaviour of the epoxy resins were carried out to reproduce the behaviour of MSMA unidirectional composites. Numerical models showed very good agreement with experimental results for the four types of composites produced, and thus provided a tool to predict the behaviour of composites, as a

function of volume fraction, geometrical arrangement, matrix and MSMA properties, which is more precise than the simple analytical iso-strain model. These models also showed that in order to reach large strains, the matrix should be selected as a material with low elastic modulus, around 5MPa. Finally, the present model did not take into account any viscoelastic behaviour of the matrix, but experimental results show that these can hinder the strain, in particular if fast actuation is sought. As a result, the matrix time-dependent properties should be carefully matched to the desired actuation properties, either to reach a slow actuation, governed by the viscoelastic behaviour of the matrix, or to reach fast actuation, in that case selecting a very soft yet elastic matrix, such as some silicones.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation under the National Research Programme NRP 62 n°406240-126120. We would like to thank Prof. Peter Müllner from Boise State University for his advice on interpretation and simulation of magnetic field induced forces in Ni-Mn-Ga, and Ms C. Grize for contributing to this study during her Master thesis.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. L'excellent Shape-memory alloys handbook. John Wiley & Sons; 2013.
- [2] V. Michaud Can shape memory alloy composites be smart? *Scripta Mater* 2004;50(2):249–53.
- [3] V. Michaud and J.-A. Manson, « Progress on processing and design of composites with embedded shape memory alloy wires », invited paper to ICAM 2003, Yokohama, Japan, October 8-13 2003, *Transactions of the Materials Research Society of Japan*, 29 n°7, pp. 3043-3048, 2004.
- [4] Sozinov A, Likhachev AA, Lanska N, Ullakko K. Giant magnetic-field-induced strain in NiMnGa seven-layered martensitic phase. *Appl Phys Lett* 2002;80(10):1746–8.
- [5] Scheerbaum N, Hinz D, Gutfleisch O, Muller KH, Schultz L. Textured polymer bonded composites with Ni–Mn–Ga magnetic shape memory particles. *Acta Mater* 2007;55(8):2707–13.
- [6] Ullakko K. Magnetically controlled shape memory alloys: a new class of actuator materials. *J Mater Eng Perform* 1996;5(3):405–9.
- [7] Kohl M, Brugger D, Ohtsuka M, Takagi T. A novel actuation mechanism on the basis of ferromagnetic SMA thin films. *Sens Actuators A: Phys* 2004;114(2): 445–50.
- [8] Feuchtwanger J, Michael S, Juang J, Bono D, OHandley RC, Allen SM, et al. Energy absorption in Ni–Mn–Ga-polymer composites. *J Appl Phys* 2003;93(10):8528–30.
- [9] Tian B, Chen F, Tong YX, Li L, Zheng YF, Liu Y. The orientation dependence of transformation strain of NiMnGa polycrystalline alloy and its composite with epoxy resin. *J Alloys Compd* 2010;505:680–4.
- [10] Hannula SP, Aaltio I, Ge Y, Lahelin M, Söderberg. Processing and properties of Ni–Mn–Ga magnetic shape memory alloy based hybrid materials. *Curr Appl Phys* 2012;12:S63–7.
- [11] Sun X, Xie C. Effect of volume fraction of NiMnGa powders on magnetic-field induced strain in NiMnGa/polymer composites. *Adv Mater Res* 2011:387–90.
- [12] Kauffmann-Weiss S, Scheerbaum N, Liu J, Klauss H, Schultz L, Mäder E, et al. Reversible magnetic field induced strain in Ni₂MnGa-polymer-composites. *Adv Eng Mater* 2012;14:20–7.
- [13] Glock S, Zhang XX, Kucza NJ, Müllner P, Michaud V. Structural, physical and damping properties of melt-spun Ni–Mn–Ga wire-epoxy composites. *Compos Part A: Appl Sci Manuf* 2014;63:68–75.
- [14] S.Glock, V. Michaud, "Thermal and damping behaviour of magnetic shape memory alloy composites", *Smart materials and Structures*, 24 (2015) 065025.
- [15] Gans E, Carman GP. Cyclic actuation of Ni–Mn–Ga composites. *J Appl Phys* 2006;99(8):084905(1)–5(4).

- [16] Kiefer B, Lagoudas DC. Magnetic field-induced martensitic variant reorientation in magnetic shape memory alloys. *Phil Mag* 2005;85(33–35):4289–329.
- [17] S. Glock, L. P. Canal, C. M. Grize, V. Michaud, "Magneto-mechanical actuation of ferromagnetic shape memory alloy/epoxy composites", *Composite Science and Technology*, Volume 114, pages 110-118, June 2015.
- [18] Sozinov A, Likhachev AA, Ullakko K. Crystal structures and magnetic anisotropy properties of Ni–Mn–Ga martensitic phases with giant magnetic field- induced strain. *IEEE Trans Magn* 2002;38(5):2814–6.